

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

AI IN THE TERMS OF EDUCATION: PROS AND CONS

Supervisor: Sadiyeva Shaxnoza Komilovna.

Teacher of the functional lexics department in English Philology faculty. UZSWLU

Yusupova Dildora Baxrom qizi

Student of English Philology Faculty, UZSWLU

yusupovadildora646@gmail.com

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15179058>

Abstract: *Artificial intelligence (AI) plays a crucial role in today's fast-paced world, it often conjures images of futuristic robots or self-driving cars, but its significance goes far beyond these examples. AI is a transformative tool that is reshaping industries, including education. For educators, AI presents a unique opportunity to reimagine traditional teaching models, offering personalized learning, alleviating administrative burdens, and providing real-time insights into student development. Students can learn different studies from Artificial Intelligence easily and it helps everyone how to solve the problems that occurs in their life in the terms of science. Because it has lots of features which makes to find or fulfill any project immediately. Cause this, it is a field of study which is resulting innovations and development that have culminated in computers, machines, and other artifacts having human-like intelligence characterized by cognitive abilities, learning, adaptability, and decision-making capabilities. Professions use it in order to perform several administrative functions such as checking and grading students' assignments more effectively and for gaining higher quality in their teaching system. Both students and teachers can create a progress in their area via working with AI technologies. However, while it has such benefits for humanity, it has some drawbacks which can influence the people's success and mind. This study shows the importance of AI in the modern world and how it affects the humanity whether negative or positive way for educational methods. Moreover, it includes some feedbacks about the most famous AI models around the world, for example, ChatGPT, DeepSeek, Gamma and Canva that are commonly used by students who lives different edge of the world. How it will be in the future with the advancement of technology?*

Key words: *Artificial Intelligence, modern subjects, AI in philology, pros and cons of AI.*

Introduction.

"Predicting the future isn't magic, it is Artificial Intelligence"- Dave Waters. Artificial intelligence is a field of science concerned with building computers and machines that can reason, learn, and act in such a way that would normally require human intelligence or that involves data whose scale exceeds what humans can analyze. In 21s' century, AI become the most powerful and innovative invention. If we consider the history of Artificial Intelligence, while Alan Turing had the famous test named after him, John McCarthy is usually acknowledged as the person who invented AI. At the gathering for a 1956 Dartmouth summer research project on

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

artificial intelligence, the coining of the term was attributed to him. This convening served as the basis for much of the early foundational development of AI theory. After this, some companies tried to develop AI technologies, for example, Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA) in the U.S. In the 1970s, invented the inventive maps which allowed people to address the right way and it was the alternative model of AI that we use today's life called "navigator".

Regarding to its role in our modern world, everything has connection with AI from our daily neseccity to world's environment whether it is chatbots or robots. For example, we use some kind of AI everyday like fridge, washing machine, vacuum cleaner, air conditioner, and others. Moreover, the interactive apps on our smartphones are also the type of AI. It is used for different purposes in the several fields like healthcare, architecture, manufacture, and education. Of course, it is essential also other spheres but those are the most importants. Firstly, AI plays a crucial role in healthcare in todays' fast-paced world since it can diagnose the illnesses with its advanced technology. We admit that if we become sick and go the hospital, we should be analyzed by AI (such as rentgen, MRT) for the first time then doctors will give consultation. There are robots in the world which can replace the role of nurses that is essential for old or disabled people. Surgeons also utilize it during the operation for balancing the patient's health condition. Secondly, AI opens new opportunities in architecture, especially, modern architects work with it in order to design the structure and decoration of the buildings as new Artificial Intelligences can draw everything dependent on your opinion. Thirdly, manufacture needs AI all the time because their job is related to technology, particularly, in the factories. AI helps them to producing more effectively and efficiently. The cause is that machines work faster than humanity so it reduces waste of time and some mistakes which are taken by people. That's why factory-made products are more chosen by consumers than man-made ones. Finally, AI is commonly used in education in the aim of improving the quality of deep learning. For teachers, it has lots of options that will be useful in teaching system. For instance, they can make visible materials and creative games which can perpetrate the lessons to be more engaging and not boring for students. If students interested in topic-based activities, they value teachers' efforts. Furthermore, AI has beneficial sides for students while their studying time. They can learn independently and deeply with it. Now, this article shows the importance of Artificial Intelligence, advantage and disadvantages of it in the terms of education.

The advantage of AI

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

Since AI become widespread in modern world and everything subservient on it, it is also be important in education. Teachers and students utilize it for various spheres and subjects like maths, mother tongue, biology, chemistry. For people who studies or works at University of literature, it can be beneficial for speaking, reading, writing and grammar. Now, I will explain respectively why they find AI the most helpful invention in those areas.

1. **Maths.** AI technologies is used more for mathematics rather than other subjects as calculating and solving puzzles are available in this field. First of all, students always tend to use it for counting the issues with huge numbers. Cause this is easy to do it with AI. Why? Because Artificial Intelligence works 100 times faster than human's. So it takes much less time rather than that of people. Moreover, students can solve some extraordinary and unknown mathematical theorem with AI as it is familiar with almost all information and matters over the world. And this can stop from overthinking which can damage student's mind. In my opinion, teachers use it less than students but they usually make the use for reasons that we have mentioned above.

2. **Biology and Chemistry.** AI mechanical tools are commonly used in this subject whether during the lesson or independently by both teachers and students. You know, in today's life, mainly subjects, especially, biology and chemistry can't be taught without advanced technology(AI). Because when they should carry out research related to topic of lesson, they need AI in the laboratory. Most actions are done by it, it shows result, it gives final feedback of experiment. Without it, nothing is possible.

3. **Speaking.** It is real that AI can communicate like human. The useful side is students can improve their speaking skills with it. For example, if students want to conversate with it and after ask from it to tell them their mistakes and teach how to speak properly, AI can speak on any topic and show mistakes that are done by students. Therefore, students can study on their own academy. Teachers use it in order to make their lesson more fascinating such as they may create some demonstrations or joyfull activities.

4. **Writing.** AI help academic people to take brilliant ideas and facts about the topic of essay or article. For instance Google Assistant, a lot of information is collected on this and teachers and students can use it while thinking about what to write. So, they can avoid from wasted and unnesecary sentences and stopping from writing.

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

5. **Reading.** Research shows that students can reach high level reading skills with AI. Due to the fact that now plenty materials and papers are available on AI models, which encourages students to read more and more. They can practise with AI and it makes them wise person.

It can give a hand to students who has natural disabilities like deafness or blindness. It means that such students can easily personlize their studies, AI can hears their voice and type, or it can type without voice.

The disadvantages of AI

As artificial intelligence continues to integrate into various sectors, its application in education is both celebrated and scrutinized. While AI holds significant potential to transform learning experiences, it also presents several disadvantages that need careful consideration that must be addressed to ensure a balanced and effective learning environment.

Following statements are some of them:

1. **AI cheating.** If students order it to give information that is strange to AI, it may present fake information. Because it can only answer according to data which is installed by inventors. This may mislead the student. For instance, mathematics. If AI give alternative version of theorem(this is not real answer), it influence the students' academic learning.

2. **Data privacy.** This is absolutely disadvantage of AI. If someone like student or teacher want to access AI, it requires personal information. But they don't know how to store it and keep it safely. Because of leraning enthusiasm, they may harm themselves via hackers.

3. **Job replacement.** Since AI becoming widely in education, teachers' role is getting lost in classroom. And if it carry on, teacher can't play vital role in students' future. Of course, it is quite "horrible".

4. **Lack of knowledge.** Because of AI, not only students, but also teachers are avoiding from deeply thinking. They have their works done to AI. When they struggle with some problem, they give it to AI tools for solving without any efford or trying to do by themselves. This means Artificial Intelligence is building our future, not us!.

Conclusion

In general, the results revealed that while students can use AI for positive ways that has beneficial sides for progressing and adapting in the classroom, it has also some concerns that may effect the students' future. Educational institutions should

XORIJY TILLARNI O'QITISHDA INNOVATSION YONDASHUVLAR NAZARIYANING AMALIYOTGA TATBIQI

mavzusidagi respublika ilmiy-amaliy anjumani

evaluate the costs and benefits of using artificial intelligence and provide the necessary training and support to teachers and students about using the educational instruments that are based on AI. It is also important to control students when they are using the AI that teachers and parents should make some limitations for usage of AI. If all actions can be taken carefully and we can learn how to work with Artificial Intelligence in the right way, we can create proper future between humanity and AI technologies!

References:

1. Ibrahim Adeshola, Adeola Praise Adepoju, "The opportunities and challenges of ChatGPT in education" (2023) <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/10494820.2023.2253858#:~:text=The%20launch%20of,AI-generated%20text>
2. Sabuj Ahmed "AI and its role in education a brief history of AI in education" (2024) https://www.researchgate.net/publication/386422997_AI_and_Its_Role_in_Education_A_Brief_History_of_AI_in_Education
3. Lara Nelson "AI and Education: What is the impact?" (2024) https://afaeducation.org/blog/ai-and-education-what-is-the-impact/?gad_source=1&gclid=CjwKCAiAzba9BhBhEiwA7glbauqladzNKXXw-LVqdHa5c_g5eE74IuuTe1ceybOJPTCCLj30Z5Ir4xoCf7cQAvD_BwE
4. Brendan Clugston, "Advantages and disadvantages of AI in education"(July 19, 2024) <https://www.ucanwest.ca/blog/education-careers-tips/advantages-and-disadvantages-of-ai-in-education>